

ANTI-VAWC ACT IMPLEMENTATION AND PERCEIVED SATISFACTION ON WOMEN AND CHILDREN PROTECTION DESK

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the extent of implementation of Anti-VAWC Act and the VAWC victims' perceived satisfaction on Women and Children Protection Desks of the 1st District of Negros Oriental. The study focused on the provisions of the facilities and amenities in the WCPD, proper implementation of the protocols and procedures in handling VAWC cases, WCPD officers' personal qualities manifested, and the description of experiences of VAWC victims. The study made use of the descriptive-correlational research design. This study utilized a researcher-made tool in the survey. The respondents of the study were the WCPD officers and the VAWC victims who sought assistance in the Women and Children Protection Desks. The participants were the VAWC victims who were willing to participate in an in-depth interview. Findings revealed that most of the VAWC victims are middle-aged adults, spouses, high school graduates, and unemployed. Most of the WCPD lack a camera and voice recorder to be used in the investigation process. The extent of implementation of the protocols and procedures and the satisfaction level of the VAWC victims were very high.

Keywords: *Women and Children Protection Desk, Violence against Women and Children*

INTRODUCTION

Various studies estimate that between 10% and 35% of women experience domestic violence at some point in their lives (Flury et. al, 2010). However, violence against women had been mostly ignored by society in the past due to the mistaken belief that whatever happened behind closed doors was the couple's private business (Cunningham & Baker, 2012).

In the Philippines, advocacy to end violence against women grew in 1986, but the enactment of most of the laws to protect Filipino women only happened in the 1990s. Among all of these moves, the enactment of the Magna Carta of Women (RA 9710) and the Anti-violence against Women and Their Children Act (RA 9262) was considered the most significant. These laws not only serve to protect women from all forms of abuse, but they also define crime against women by a spouse or partner as public crimes (Estrellado & Loh, 2013).

Section 9 of Republic Act 9710, Magna Carta for Women, emphasized that the state shall ensure that all women shall be protected from all forms of violence as provided for in existing laws. Agencies of government shall give priority to the defense and protection of women against gender-based offenses and help women attain justice and healing.

In Republic Act 8551, Philippine National Police Reform and Reorganization Act of 1998 (section 57), the PNP has been mandated to establish women's desks in all police stations throughout the country to administer and attend to cases involving abuses committed against women and children and other similar offenses and (section 58) to prioritize the recruitment and training of women who shall serve in the women's desk.

Women are sometimes put to blame as the cause of their own misery. Some women are accused of being "naggers" or neglectful of their duties as wives; that is why they are beaten by their spouses (PCW, 2010). For women to report in the first place requires a great deal of resilience to re-live the incident. In many countries, women know that they are overwhelmingly more likely to be blamed than believed (UN, 2019). With this, there are numerous instances where victims-survivors are unable to get the necessary services and interventions they need. They end up suffering in silence and may possibly become victims again. Lack of support, a poor justice system, and economic dependence on their abusers usually result in unreported and repetitive abuse (PCW, 2012).

Therefore, the Women and Children Protection Desk played very significant roles for providing assistance to victims of violence against women. Hence, this study aimed to gather the level of implementation of WCPD officers and the level of satisfaction of the victims of violence against women who sought assistance from the Women and Children Protection Desk of the PNP.

Research Questions

This study determines the extent of the implementation of anti-VAWC and perceived satisfaction on women and children protection desks. It answered the following specific question:

1. To what extent is the implementation of the protocols and procedures by the Women and Children Protection Desk with regard to Anti-VAWC Act as perceived by the WCPD officers?
 2. What is the satisfaction level of VAWC victims in the WCPD officers' implementation of protocols and procedures?
 3. What is the satisfaction level of the VAWC victims to the personal qualities manifested by the WCPD officers?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research method employed in this study was quantitative. Quantitatively, this study utilized the descriptive-correlational method of research using a self-made questionnaire as the main tool in gathering data.

It was descriptive since it described the level of implementation of the protocols and procedures and the qualities of the WCPD officers in handling VAWC cases. It also described the level of satisfaction as perceived by the victims toward the assistance of the Women and Children Protection Desk with regard to their protocols and procedures and the personal qualities of the WCPD officers.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the seven municipalities and two cities of the 1st District of Negros Oriental. Based on the 2015 census, the municipalities had populations ranging from 30,945 (Jimalalud) to 46,303 (Ayungon), while Guihulngan (95,969) and Canlaon (54,509) were the two cities included. Each locality had two to three Women and Children Protection Desk (WCPD) officers assigned to handle cases. From January to October 2019, reported incidents of violations of the Anti-VAWC Act (RA 9262) varied: Manjuyod (22), Ayungon (14), Guihulngan (12), Canlaon (9), Tayasan (8), Vallehermoso (8), Jimalalud (7), Bindoy (5), and La Libertad (2).

Statistical Tools

The researcher utilized statistical tools in analyzing the data gathered. Specifically, the weighted mean was used to determine the extent of implementation of the Anti-VAWC Act by the Women and Children Protection Desks and to assess the level of satisfaction of the VAWC victims. Meanwhile, the Mann-Whitney U Test was employed to test the null hypotheses.

Research Respondents

The study focused on the VAWC victims who have reported to the WCPD officers in the municipalities and cities of the 1 st District of Negros Oriental. Respondents were selected based on their willingness to participate in the study.

Research Instrument

This study used a researcher-made questionnaire to gather data. The researcher thoroughly studied the VAW Desk Manual and other important bases for the construction of the questionnaires. To ensure the legitimacy of the content, the questionnaires were subjected for perusal by a panel of experts as well as her adviser to make sure that the intention of the study is covered. The questionnaires were also presented to three (3) senior women police officers assigned in the Women and Children Protection Desks.

Suitable changes and corrections were made to ensure that the questions are clear and understandable to the respondents. The items in the self-made questionnaires revealed valid and reliable measures. The 10-item questionnaire revealed valid and reliable measures for protocols and procedures with alpha coefficient of 0.730, and the 15-item questionnaire revealed valid and reliable measures for the personal qualities of the WCPD officers with alpha coefficient of 0.860.

Data Gathering Procedure and Analysis

For the WCPD questionnaire, the researcher asked permission from the Chiefs of Police of the different police offices in the 1 st District of Negros Oriental to allow her to conduct a survey with the WCPD officers. After approval, the researcher answered the first part of the questionnaire by examining their respective WCPD office. The second and third part of the WCPD questionnaire were answered by the WCPD officers and were collected right away after all items had been answered.

For the victims, the researcher asked permission to the municipal and city mayors of the 1 st District of Negros Oriental. After approval, letters were sent to the victims to ask permission to answer for a survey regarding the subject matter. To those who responded positively, schedules were set with the respondents to avoid inconveniences or unpreparedness on their part. Confidentiality of their responses was assured and that no names will be mentioned in any part of the study. The questionnaires were retrieved and data were tabulated and treated based on the problems asked in the study.

Using the microsoft excel application, results were tallied and sent to the statistician for the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered.

RESULTS

The extent of implementation and perceived satisfaction level on the Women and Children Protection Desk.

Table 1
Extent of Implementation of the Protocols and Procedures by Women and Children Protection Desk with Regard to Anti-VAWC Act as Perceived by the WCPD Officers

Indicators	Weighted mean	Verbal Description	Extent of Implementation
The WCPD uses language or dialect that is understood by the victim-survivor.	5.00	Always	Very High
The victim is informed of her rights.	5.00	Always	Very High
The victim is informed of the processes involved in her quest for justice.	5.00	Always	Very High
The victim is taken to the nearest clinic or hospital if there is a need of further medical attention.	4.95	Always	Very High
The victim's situations have been assessed by getting basic information that can determine present and possible risks.	4.89	Always	Very High
The victim is informed of the possible solutions and remedies available to her.	4.89	Always	Very High
The victim is comfortable, in a safe and private room or area.	4.84	Always	Very High
The victim is referred to the appropriate offices which can better attend to her needs (e.g., DSWD, BLDU, TESDA).	4.74	Always	Very High
The victim has given water and other immediate needs such as food, first aid, and clothing.	4.63	Always	Very High
The victim is stable when the interview has been conducted.	4.58	Always	Very High
Composite	4.85	Always	Very High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Implementation
	4.21–5.00	Always	Very High
	3.41–4.20	Very Often	High
	2.61–3.40	Sometimes	Moderate
	1.81–2.60	Rarely	Low
	1.00–1.80	Never	Very Low

Table 2
Satisfaction Level of VAWC Victims in the WCPD Officers' Implementation of
Protocols and Procedures (n = 71)

Indicators	Weighted mean	Verbal Description	Level of Satisfaction
The WCPD uses language or dialect that I understood.	4.92	Fully Satisfied	Very High
I was stable when the interview has been conducted.	4.90	Fully Satisfied	Very High
I was comfortable, in a safe and private room or area.	4.83	Fully Satisfied	Very High
I believe that whenever necessary the WCPD will be able to take me to the nearest clinic or hospital if there is a need of further medical attention.	4.77	Fully Satisfied	Very High
My situation has been assessed by getting basic information that can determine present and possible risks.	4.68	Fully Satisfied	Very High
The WCPD informed me of my rights	4.54	Fully Satisfied	Very High
The WCPD informed me of the possible solutions and remedies available for me.	4.31	Fully Satisfied	Very High
The WCPD informed me of the processes involved in my quest for justice.	4.17	Satisfied	High
I was referred to the appropriate offices which can better attend to my needs (e.g., DSWD for psychological assessment, Barangay for BPO).	3.87	Satisfied	High
The WCPD provided me with my immediate needs (such as water, food, first aid, and clothing).	2.94	Satisfied	High
Composite	4.39	Fully Satisfied	Very High

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Satisfaction
4.21–5.00	Fully Satisfied	Very High
3.41–4.20	Satisfied	High
2.61–3.40	Moderately Satisfied	Moderate
1.81–2.60	Slightly Satisfied	Low
1.00–1.80	Dissatisfied	Very Low

Table 3
Satisfaction Level of the VAWC Victims to the Personal Qualities Manifested by the WCPD Officers (n = 71)

The WCPD officer ...	Weighted mean	Verbal Description	Level of Satisfaction
has expressed the right body movements and has expressed the right facial expression	4.73	Fully Satisfied	Very High
is respectful and uttered the right words	4.68	Fully Satisfied	Very High
deals only with the proper authorities who are involved in the situation	4.66	Fully Satisfied	Very High
is being honest and straightforward	4.63	Fully Satisfied	Very High
kept the situation from turning from bad to worse	4.61	Fully Satisfied	Very High
is calm or composed	4.58	Fully Satisfied	Very High
is diplomatic and is willing to wait	4.55	Fully Satisfied	Very High
guards, secures, and protects the confidentiality of information, situation, or pieces of evidence	4.55	Fully Satisfied	Very High
is genuine	4.54	Fully Satisfied	Very High
values equal responsibilities and equal opportunities of women and men and girls and boys	4.52	Fully Satisfied	Very High
understands gender equality as a basic human right	4.49	Fully Satisfied	Very High
is capable or is willing to endure	4.48	Fully Satisfied	Very High
is forgiving in the middle of tension, crisis, or emergency situations	4.45	Fully Satisfied	Very High
values or makes sense of the situation	4.37	Fully Satisfied	Very High

has been able to share and feel my sorrow or tragedy	4.34	Fully Satisfied	Very High
Composite	4.54	Fully Satisfied	Very High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Satisfaction
	4.21–5.00	Fully Satisfied	Very High
	3.41–4.20	Satisfied	High
	2.61–3.40	Moderately Satisfied	Moderate
	1.81–2.60	Slightly Satisfied	Low
	1.00–1.80	Dissatisfied	Very Low

DISCUSSION

The study delved into the extent of implementation and perceived satisfaction level on the Women and Children Protection Desk of the Anti-VAWC Act.

Table 1 shows the extent of implementation of the protocols and procedures as perceived by the WCPD officers. It has been shown that the results are all very high. This just means that all the WCPD officers have always implemented the protocols and procedures as written in the VAW Desk Manual and the PNP Manual for First Responders. The findings are consistent with the study of Naganag (2022), which reported that victim-survivors experienced the PNP Women and Children Protection Desk as effectively implementing the required mandatory services, along with other government-provided interventions and entitlements.

Every individual is entitled to equal protection and rights regardless of age, race, color, nationality, language, status, religion/faith, political or other opinion, ethnic/cultural or social origin, disability, property, birth, or other status (PCW and IAC-VAWC, 2012). According to the Barangay VAW Desk Manual (2012), officers should be properly and thoroughly educated on gender-based violence. Through their insights, they can help create change in their communities, including a change in attitudes, beliefs, and practices that would reject all forms of violence.

Police officers are known as being the first respondents of the five pillars of the criminal justice system. They are often called upon to intervene when an act of violence is in progress or shortly after it has occurred. Police officers work with victims, offenders, witnesses, and various forms of evidence. Their response can have a dramatic impact on ensuing developments, including the prevention of future violent acts and the protection of victims (Handbook on Effective Police Response to Violence against Women, 2010). Under the PNP Investigative Directive 2012-059, the investigation of cases involving gender-based violence shall be under the jurisdiction of the Women and Children Protection Desk. As such, it shall be confidential and must be investigated by trained WCPD investigators. Also, the victims will be afforded the necessary protection and be extended with assistance to prevent their re-victimization.

As presented in Table 2, seven out of ten items in the protocols and procedures have a very high level of satisfaction from the VAWC victims. The item with the highest

satisfaction rating among VAWC victims with 4.92 is the usage of the WCPD of the language or dialect that is understood by the victim. The item with the second highest rating of satisfaction with 4.90 is when the VAWC victims were stable when the interview was conducted by the WCPD officers.

The discipline of criminal justice tends to focus on the offender. However, the victim's cooperation with authorities, which often begins with a willingness to report the crime, is central to a successful investigation and prosecution (Fisher, 2014). A VAW victim's satisfaction is a good sign that the criminal justice system for abused women is reliable. It is safe to interpret that with regard to the services of the Women and Children Protection Desk, the PNP Mission has fulfilled "to enforce the law, to prevent and control crimes, to maintain peace and order, and to ensure public safety and internal security with the active support of the community."

Of the ten items, three items are rated by the VAWC victims as satisfied. Though it is still high, the provision of immediate needs such as food, water, or first aid has the lowest satisfaction rating with 2.94 . The law enforcers must establish mechanisms to ensure that crime victims and their families receive necessary emergency assistance. Crime victims may need food, clothing, temporary shelter, or housing (IACP, 2000). In the PNP Manual (2008), the officer on duty assures the victim that immediate assistance will be given and sees to it that this is done.

The second item with least satisfaction from the VAWC victims is the protocol which requires the VAWC victims to be referred to other agencies which can better attend to their needs with 3.87. The VAW Desk should refer VAW victims to the proper agencies or institutions in cases they need services such as legal assistance, psychosocial services (e.g., counselling, psychiatric examination, and therapy), and livelihood development and employment assistance (Barangay VAW Desk Manual, 2012). This finding is corroborated by a similar study conducted by the United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Western Asia (United Nations ESCWA, 2022) in its report entitled "Service Provider Coordination and Referral Systems in the Arab Region to Address Violence against Women and Girls." The report revealed weak linkages between public, national, and humanitarian referral mechanisms, resulting in parallel systems rather than mutually reinforcing processes.

Table 3 shows the satisfaction level of the VAWC victims to the personal qualities manifested by the WCPD officers during their reporting of an incident of violations of Anti-VAWC Act. Surprisingly, the level of satisfaction of all items is very high. This result proved that VAW victims-survivors may be more comfortable relating their experiences to a fellow woman (Philippine Commission on Women, 2012). Females give attention to social stimulations such as human faces and voices females are stronger empathizers (Margalit, 2015).

As violence against women is a human rights violation, all assistance and protection efforts should strive for the restoration of the victim's rights and prevent further violations (PCW and IAC-VAWC, 2012). It begins with the understanding of gender equality as a basic human right. The WCPD officer values equal rights, responsibilities,

and opportunities of women and men and girls and boys (Manual for Police First Responders, 2010).

The WCPD is open 24 hours and is ready to receive complaints and calls for assistance anytime. The officer on duty assures the victim that immediate assistance will be given and sees to it that this is done (Manual for Police First Responders 2010). In dealing with VAW victims, according to the Manual for Police First responders (2010), a WCPD officer must be accepting and non-judgmental. A WCPD officer must be sensitive and sincere. The police officer must conduct all investigations in a manner that respects the rights and needs of each woman without needlessly adding to the existing burden experienced by the victim (Manual for Police First Responders, 2010). A WCPD officer must be patient and understanding and empathetic (Manual for Police First Responders, 2010).

Conclusions

Overall, WCPD officers have demonstrated a strong commitment to following protocols and procedures for every VAWC victim they assist. This dedication has resulted in a very high satisfaction level among victims regarding the officers' professional conduct and personal qualities. Despite this success, the study highlights critical areas for enhancement. Specifically, victim satisfaction was notably lower for the provision of immediate needs, such as food and water, and for the protocol requiring referral to other agencies. It is also essential to improve the procedure for informing victims about their legal options and the steps involved in their pursuit of justice.

Recommendations

Improving the response to violence against women and children requires a series of targeted actions. A key recommendation is to proactively disseminate information on the Anti-VAWC Act to empower women with knowledge of their rights and available legal remedies. This can be achieved by utilizing social media platforms and distributing brochures at strategic venues where women frequently gather, such as 4Ps and PTA meetings, and barangay assemblies. To ensure immediate physical security, local government units are urged to make their local crisis centers fully operational, providing safe havens for women and children in distress. Furthermore, to address the hesitation some women feel in approaching law enforcement, the creation of a confidential Women's Helpline is recommended to provide a safe channel for inquiries and reporting. For a truly effective intervention, it is essential to conduct psychological assessments for both victims and their children, followed by necessary therapeutic interventions. Finally, to break the cycle of violence, rehabilitation programs should be made available for abusive partners, particularly in cases where victims have chosen to forgive them. These recommendations are all foundational elements for a proposed Strategic Development Plan aimed at strengthening both the empowerment of women and the capabilities of the agencies supporting them.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this research, the privacy of participants was strictly observed. Anonymity and confidentiality were ensured, and all participants were required to provide informed consent. Artificial intelligence (AI) applications, including ChatGPT and Gemini AI, were used in this study to refine and enhance the construction of sentences for greater coherence and precision.

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